

Numerical and experimental analysis of selected nonlinear beam dynamics in multimode fibres

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Abstract—We discuss a numerical model and experimental results to study the effect of spatial beam self-cleaning in nonlinear graded-index fibers and how to control such process, including transient phenomena. We examine illustrative some cases of coherent combination of cleaned beams and supercontinuum generation.

Keywords— *multimode nonlinear fibre optics, beam propagation method, optical beam shaping*

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent studies in nonlinear multimode fibre optics have unveiled a diverse range of outcomes, combining the flexibility of beam shaping in free space optics with the high-power density of guided optics [1,2]. Notably, research has concentrated, among numerous other directions, on spatial beam self-cleaning [3] and its thermodynamical interpretation [4,5], nonlinear beam shaping, supercontinuum generation, and the application of multimode fibres in new fibre lasers [6,7]. In this work, we

present experimental results and numerical simulations focusing on specific dynamics of beam propagation, particularly the coherent combining of self-cleaned beams [8]. In the numerical simulation of an idealised uniform weakly guiding graded-index (GRIN) fibre, the refractive index profile assumes the form of a truncated paraboloid along the transverse coordinates x, y . Beyond this model, the presence of random stress or bending along the fibre leading to linear mode coupling can be incorporated by weakly varying the refractive index $n(x, y, z)$ along the propagation coordinate z , with the introduction of a coarse step in the numerical integration. Guided modes can also be coupled nonlinearly due to the contribution of the Kerr effect, and its coefficient γ is related to the fibre glass nonlinearity.

II. COHERENT COMBINING OF SELF-CLEANED BEAMS

When temporal modal walk-off is negligible (long pulse), a multimode beam may exhibit low spatial coherence (speckles) while preserving temporal coherence. As a result, stable interference fringes can be observed when two self-cleaned beams are combined, even after several meters of fibre propagation. To fully analyse the coherent combination of self-cleaned beams, the numerical model should be also extended to the spectral effects and light polarisation. Pulsed beams can be susceptible to spectral broadening, which may subsequently affect the visibility of fringes. Similarly, the polarisation of light

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also plays a role in this phenomenon. Equation 1 can incorporate the material dispersion $D(\omega)$, and the wavelength dependence of diffraction, polarization and Kerr effect:

$$-i \frac{\partial \tilde{A}}{\partial z} = \left(\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2}{2k(\omega)} + D(\omega) - k(\omega) \Delta \frac{r^2}{R^2} \right) \tilde{A} + \gamma \mathcal{F} \left[\left(|A|^2 + \frac{2}{3} |B|^2 \right) A \right] \quad (1)$$

The refractive index profile of eq.1 explicitly exhibits a parabolic shape for $r \leq R$, where $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$, Δ is the relative refractive index difference, R is the fibre core radius and γ is related to the fibre glass Kerr nonlinearity. Overall, this equation (or its monochromatic limit) permits to reproduce certain effects, including spatial beam self-cleaning and the attainment of thermodynamically equilibrium distribution among the modes, as will be discussed in the presentaton, but also to explore particular beam dynamics such as the nonlinear selection of guided modes and is particularly well-suited for highly multimodal beams. $\tilde{A}(x, y, \omega - \omega_0)$ denotes the complex envelope around ω_0 of a specific polarisation component, $A(x, y, t)$ the time-domain envelope and $\mathcal{F}[\cdot]$ indicates the time Fourier transform. The Kerr effect includes both self and cross phase modulation from the other polarisation component, $\tilde{B}(x, y, \omega - \omega_0)$, whose corresponding equation can be derived by interchanging A, \tilde{A} with B, \tilde{B} in eq.1. This method is computationally expensive, but numerically solving eq.1 offers flexibility, allowing for the inclusion of further factors like fibre tapering or gain. Figure 1 summarises a series of experimental results (see ref. [8] for details) of coherent beam combining of two self-cleaned beams, each of which was obtained in a 12-meter-long segment of GRIN fibre. The combined output beam passes through a diffraction grating, allowing the image to display the spatial profile in the vertical coordinate and the wavelength in the horizontal coordinate. The horizontal fringes are the results of the coherent beam combining and disappear when the end of one of the arms is blocked. We observe that with 60-ps pulses and kW-level peak power, the beam exhibits power-dependent self-phase modulation-induced spectral broadening. Notably, the beam cleaning and subsequent occupation of the low-order modes are discernible at the spectral extreme, while the spectrum's centre is predominantly depleted and speckled. These experimental results show how the modal distribution can exhibit significant variations along the temporal spectrum. The numerical solution of eq.1 gives qualitatively similar results to those shown in fig.2. To reduce computational time, the pulse duration and fibre length were reduced to 10 ps and 1.5m, respectively. Panel (a) presents the beam iso-intensity surface along the GRIN fibre propagation in one of the arms (all spectrum). Panel (b) illustrates the outcome after applying a function that simulates the dispersive spectroscop. In line with the experiments shown in fig.1, the depletion and linear speckles are visible in the centre of the spectrum, while the beam intensity concentrates on the spectral wings. Another arm replicates the simulation, using a different realisation of the random mode coupling, and panel (c) illustrates the presence of the horizontal fringes when the two beams are combined, with results qualitatively similar to fig.1

Fig. 1. Experimental results of coherent combining of self-cleaned beams upon input peak power.

Fig. 2. (a) numerical simulations of beam propagation in 1.5m long GRIN fibre with NA=0.2; input Gaussian beam diameter 40 μ m FWHMI, peak intensity 5GW/cm²; (b) output results upon spectrum and one of the transverse coordinates; (c) numerical simulation of coherent beam combining of self-cleaned beams.

III. CONCLUSIONS

We compare experimental results of nonlinear beam propagation in multimode fibres with the full numerical solution of the governing equation, considering temporal spectral and polarisation effects. Although it necessitates extensive numerical simulations, this method is capable of reproducing qualitatively phenomena such as the coherent superposition of self-cleaned beams.

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